

Spectrum Analysis

Digital Arts-and-Culture Assets and the Future of Co-Creating Decentralised Technologies

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Abstract

The rise of decentralized ledger (bookkeeping) systems that operate as public transaction archives to store value records (such as payments in a cryptocurrency) and maintain consensus about agreements also seems to promise solutions for the problem of scaling trust-based decision-making processes. Once linked almost exclusively to finance (“cryptocurrencies”), the “blockchain space” has become a terrain of social and technological experimentation. While these changes are likely to substantially transform the way, we organize our collective actions, few digital content creators; artists, designers, and other actors not directly linked to processes of technological innovation are currently involved. In this essay, we describe how such a co-creative approach to such involvement can be developed through the public prototyping of Spectrum, a blockchain-based tool for digital creators. What we found is that such an approach offers opportunities to more fully comprehend value chains, but also highlights need for co-creation approaches that cut across existing audiences and bring in new actors. This matters because blockchain-based strategies for technology design are about to transform the way we create, share, and cooperate. Given the promise and potential stakes of shifting the creation of digital arts-and-cultural assets to infrastructures based on such distributed ledger technologies, it is crucial that artists and other digital creators engage with the design both of these infrastructures and the systems of governance structuring their operation.

Keywords: *Digital arts-and-culture assets, blockchain, decentralised technologies, co-creative design, open data*

1 Introduction

In this paper, we engage with a specific technology development process, whose aim is the creation of a digital assets catalogue that operates as a tool for artists as well as tool of analysis, facilitating the comprehension of how actors across value chains approach digital assets creation. Spectrum analysis describes an applied arts-and-technology research project that aims to involve users in a concrete design process to engage with questions and processes that in turn frame our (co-creative) activity across micro-, meso- and macro-scales. Over a two-year period, we have worked with Spectrum to offer exemplary engagement with this dynamic. Spectrum aims to offer a blockchain-based digital assets catalogue for digital creative industries. After several iterations it is now available for user testing. In these use scenarios, we showcase the project's history of software development and involve actors from government, research, enterprise, and society in user testing. In this essay, we focus on music as a well-developed use case with a strong commitment from many actors across these four sectors; we have also identified the field of open cultural data as exemplary transfer dynamic that raises additional issues involving the question of continued enrichment of existing digital assets through co-created metadata. These two complementary concerns reflect our interest in comprehending the way in which blockchain-based approaches can transform entire value chains.

Through the design of specific tools, blockchain-based approaches might help us address broader issues of trust in processes of tracing and attributing contributions in co-creative and open innovation contexts (Shavit 2016). Our own research is framed by related work across this space of social and technological experimentation. While industry actors are already exploring the future of royalty collection (cf. URights, a research initiative of IBM and the French collecting society SACEM), artist-coders such as Imogen Heap have been among the pioneers in this space (Howard 2015) and initiatives such as "Artists Re:Thinking the Blockchain" affirm the need to broaden the range of people and perspectives involved in these experiments beyond a small core of software developers (Catlow et al 2017). Explorations of value systems in collaborative contexts serve as reminder that blockchain-based approaches build on a much broader dynamic of peer-to-peer cultures and collaborative economies (Pazaitis et al 2017).

1 Methodology

Spectrum Analysis

With Spectrum, a DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology) platform, a proof of concept exists, a prototyping dynamic has been initiated and a validation phase has been

organized. In a next step, the aim is to elaborate a corresponding co-creation approach with a focus on the involvement of artists / digital creators. What follows is an account of how we approach this iteration of co-creation methods.

Project History

05/16	24 Hrs Electronic, Luxembourg - <i>Rocklab - Cultural institution - From awareness to education</i>
11/16	Sonic Visions Panel presentation: Creativity + Technology = new opportunities? Luxembourg
12/16	EU Creative Hubs network (Formalisation of initial digital assets life cycles), Edinburgh Music - creators
04/17	10th edition of Luxembourg intellectual property day, Smart royalties topic, Luxembourg
05/17	24 Hrs Electronic demo, Luxembourg
09/17	1535 creative hub demo, Luxembourg
11/17	Sonic visions demo, Transforming DRM, from sound to blockchain, Luxembourg
02/18	Spectrum - A D-DAC (Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue) transforming digital assets administration, Luxembourg
05/18	24 Hrs Electronic demo, Luxembourg
06/18	Sonar Market Lab installation, Barcelona

Current status

Spectrum is an exploratory project that aims to test how blockchain-based technologies can simplify the administration of digital creative assets. Spectrum is a D-DAC (Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue) that explores sustainable alternatives for resolving digital media industry complexities at the various stages of digital assets life cycle: creation, production and distribution, archiving and reuse. The core aim of this project is to provide a technical test platform to digital creative industries players allowing them:

1. To identify and validate candidate blockchain fields of use;
2. To get an acute understanding of whether (and if so, how) their products and related technical as well business operations can benefit from an added value with the Blockchain technology (on the basis of relevant minimal testing).

Focus areas are:

- Digital assets
- User community value exchange
- Blockchain based operations benchmarks
- Public and private permission blockchains
- Smart contracts
- Tokens

At the current stage, the Spectrum “D-DAC Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue” is a consolidation of players in the Luxembourg blockchain ecosystem, and the test use-cases are being developed in the digital entertainment and creative industries across Europe. This collaborative initiative, supported by the Intrachain network and the Digital Luxembourg initiative, is carried by:

- Technoport SA – a technology-oriented business incubator promoting and supporting the development of innovative companies in Luxembourg
- Sonopraxis – a digital art & science consultancy company
- Bitbank – a Luxembourg Blockchain Start-up that builds decentralised applications and provides consultancy services
- APLA – a blockchain platform for organising economic, public and social activities through smart laws and smart contracts

Conceptual Issues: New Stakes, New Stakeholders

If these developments introduce new stakes, we also have new stakeholders, some of whom are already engaging with these dynamics but many are not. The task for co-creation approaches is fairly large - it ranges from new ways to “map” stakeholders and value chains to finding ways to actually engage them across these value chains.

Blockchain is a technological enabler depending on a distributed governance model. The design of governance model can and must be co-creative for facilitating interoperability. When we speak of governance, we assume that we can comprehend the point and process of creative production (example: Spectrum), but also that we can follow (and track) the digital object throughout its lifecycle across complete value chains. This extends far beyond a revival of digital rights management; instead, this is a question of how we comprehend the operation (and governability) of digital objects.¹²

While technology development seems to just happen and it is all around us, one

¹² While such conceptual issues are beyond the methodological scope of this essay, we think it important to address the question of digital objects in distributed environments. For the idea of an “entropology” addressing the condition of distribution, see Rossiter & Zehle 2017.

question for co-creation methods is whether and how arts and culture can become key drivers and even (re)claim the lead in tech development. Possible audiences include: People who love blockchains. People who have no idea what a blockchain is. People who are worried about blockchains. People who love music and digital creation. People who care about how artists can make a living in digital economies. Artists /Digital creative interested in co-creating technology. We want these different audiences to meet and mix, and we need a co-creation approach that can work with the differences and commonalities of these audiences.

Conceptual Issues: New Value Chains, New Data Models - The Examples of Music

The internet has been made for digital data transfer along a community of researchers; the network used by this community has been the seed for digital data transfer at a worldwide scale. Nowadays, digital data becomes more and more valuable, and Blockchain allows secure peer-to-peer transaction of digital asset. In this global context, Blockchain appears to be a powerful tool for digital value exchange in a secure and fully trusted way, providing the following technical capabilities:

- Decentralised infrastructure, spread over a network;
- Peer-to-peer model for direct operation;
- Build-in trust;
- Resilience, high security;
- Historical conservation - capacity for audit trail and business intelligence.

The initial challenge for the digital media and entertainment industry players to exploit decentralised technologies capabilities is to validate blockchain best candidate use-case along collaborative value chains. The music industry is very dynamic in embracing new technologies from creation to distribution. Significant DLT (Decentralised Ledger Technologies) research for decentralised rights management have been operated since 2015 (Fujimura 2015). This research focused on the technological capability of adding the rights related information within a blockchain transaction. On an operational perspective what still needs to be investigated is the end to end value proposal of decentralised technologies for a musical digital asset. Within the spectrum project we have mapped representative operational processes involved in the generation of a digital asset in the music industry. We have designed a musical digital assets life cycle to point out the different processes where decentralised technologies can potentially bring an added value. We have illustrated 5 processes of musical digital assets generation, 1. Creation, 2. Production, 3. Artwork, 4. Distribution and marketing, 5. Investments and revenue management. Illustrated in the figure below are the activities where operating actors of the music

industry are expecting a facilitated process with decentralised digital assets management technologies.

Creation process: Digital music creators are seeking for solutions to administer rights repartition/recognition in the early phase of musical digital asset generation. Ex. Collaborations across musicians, singers, vocalists, writers through smart contracts.

Production process: Recording professional music requires studio resources. Music professionals are seeking for indirect facilitation from decentralised technologies to leverage the necessary funds to book studio capabilities. The expected solution by music professionals is to use the smart contracts to raise funds under different modes; Love money, Crowdsourcing, label support.

Figure 1. Digital assets life cycle model and decentralised technologies impact (Technoport, 2017)

Assets & artworks: Musical recordings release impact is nowadays much related to graphical and video related content. The expectations of music professional is to be able to include artwork professionals in smart contracts for potential future share of revenue. A kind of media for equity deal.

Distribution and marketing: The expectation of music professional is to be able to use a smart contract and related content to facilitate organisation of concerts and for example to deal real time revenue sharing on ticket sales.

Investment & revenue management: Music professionals' expectations is heavily related to the capabilities of Decentralised Digital Assets Management to facilitate fund raising, royalties' collections, direct retribution from unit sales activities.

2 Assessment / State of Research

With the spectrum project we have demonstrated how to operate the formalisation of a digital asset at the early collaboration phases of creative digital asset generation. Digital creatives can access and use a Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue (D-DAC) to register their creative works and trigger collaborations across the various parties involved in the digital assets value chain. Although we have a robust technological layer enabling Decentralised Digital Assets Management, we still need to formalise and validate swift collaboration processes and related technological interfaces to involve all the contributing parties of the digital asset life cycle to exploit the full capability and benefits of decentralised technologies. Our latest development scope of the spectrum project was to add the archiving activities and related private and public parties involved.

On the basis of existing digital assets generation life cycle, various areas of trade, financial related transactions supported by fintech technologies currently exist. From the initial collaboration to co-create an asset to production and distribution there are multiple existing trade touchpoints that are administered by rights/financial uncorrelated third parties. Financial trade technologies of digital creative assets are emerging and are facilitating the tack of digital creators to trade their creative assets, request crowdfunding, monetize production. Operating these trade processes requires much technological and human effort that can be simplified with decentralised technologies. We believe that adopting a living-lab approach will support us to generalise the use of Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue across existing collaboration processes and not only re-defining collaboration processes for technology adoption. Industry standards such as DDEX in the music industry and fintech industry standards such as FIBO (Financial Industry Business Ontology) have shown how defining governance models of technological capabilities is relevant to ensure technological adoption. Our next development step of the Spectrum project will focus on the definition of governance models with the support of organisations such as Infrachain in Luxembourg that supports community-driven governance for operational Blockchains.

At Technoport, we have set with the Spectrum project the initial technological and inclusive operational layers (integrating independent digital creative assets creators, private production companies and content aggregators, public cultural heritage archiving organisation and art & culture research organisation and academic bodies)

providing a test platform to address the mentioned challenges by using a Decentralised Digital Assets Catalogue (D-DAC). In future collaborations (including K8), This D-DAC based on DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology) principles will evolve to reach an optimal fit to various categories of digital assets life cycles: creation, production and distribution, archiving. We currently have the technical test platform to invite digital creative industries players to test and co-design Prosumer functionalities. This operated under a living lab mode will support the definition of governance models for Decentralised Rights Administration under collaboratively approved data ontology to reach shared standards.

3 Perspectives: From Creation to Co-Creation - The Example of Open Cultural Data

To focus on the generation of digital creative assets is to focus on the moment of creation itself. In all philosophies of art and culture, this moment is elusive, and we tend to resort to ideas of inspiration, or the intensity of collaborative engagement that somehow defies description. At the same time, the data-based processes of digital creation provide a wide range of information. Leaving aside the question of whether something like a “decisive moment” defining the moment of creative expression even exists (and thus whether it can be attributed to a specific creator at all), this means that someone (or some process) has to decide which of these data points “marks” the moment in the flow of data which then becomes the reference for the digital object - the version of the image, the movie, the song. However, all of this only refers to the moment of creation.¹³

If we shift the focus of analysis toward the potential of co-creation, it matters to what extent we can also consider moments of co-creation across the lifecycle of a digital object, and how we inscribe the traces of (co-creative) use into the metadata of digital objects. For the creation of arts and culture, this may or may not be a central concern.¹⁴ But for arts and culture institutions, this is becoming a key issue - from the co-curation of exhibitions to the integration of co-created metadata into the archive of digital objects. And many of these are potential application fields for blockchain-based

¹³ In a 1952 collection of his works, the photographer Henri Cartier-Bresson famously defined the “decisive moment” as follows: “To me, photography is the simultaneous recognition, in a fraction of a second, of the significance of an event as well as of a precise organization of forms which give that event its proper expression.” See Cartier-Bresson 2014.

¹⁴ In the realm of literature, co-created material is sometimes referred to as “fan fiction”, see Burt 2017; in gaming, discussion has revolved around the roles (and possible remuneration) of “modders” (fan coders), since mods extend the life of games and play a key role in the digital asset management strategies of game publishers. For an early contribution to this ongoing controversy, see Kücklich 2005.

approaches.

To explore these possibilities, it makes sense to move from mapping collections to mapping the lifecycles of the digital objects in the archives that make up these collections. Seemingly static terms like “storage” may be misleading, as is the idea of the archive itself - unless we think of it as a living archive whose contents continue to be enriched and linked throughout a lifetime of use.

Recent efforts to address this include a series of initiatives by Mediachain Labs to create an “attribution engine” (a search engine for images with open licenses) and a “social impact” cryptocurrency without any transaction fees for end-users. Mediachain Labs offers a useful example because they started to address the key role of users in value creation: “Users generate the value of these networks, but individual users must cede ownership of their contributions, losing even basic attribution as their work is shared and propagated. ... We believe that the only way out of the incumbent-dominated internet is for emerging platforms to cooperate, leveraging open data and decentralised applications to distribute the “network effect” across a community of creators, users, developers and organizations.” Their solution was the mediachain, “a collaborative federated media metadata protocol that allows parties to make statements about creative works” (Nazarov 2016a).

Mediachain Labs also addressed the potential of open cultural data. They noted that “[i]nstitutions generally publish their open data through their proprietary APIs or as static data dumps on Github. The datasets live in disparate silos, unaware of each other’s existence. ... Furthermore, fractured datasets lead to fractured APIs— developers hoping to use open data must accept the burden of interacting with multiple incompatible APIs. This friction inhibits reuse” (Nazarov 2016b). So, for “openness” to mean “lower thresholds for use and reuse”, appropriate data models and APIs are needed. Instead, reuse tends to create even more silos: “If a developer creates an application that generates valuable new metadata supplementing an original dataset, it’s typically placed in a new silo since contributing it back to the source presents technological and curatorial challenges” (ibid.). Aware of the painful process of establishing new standards (such as JSON-ID), Mediachain’s open source solution (based on the peer-to-peer hypermedia protocol IPFS) was not a new standard but a “reconciliator layer” that automatically linked disparate data sets describing the same object (ibid.). Mediachain Labs was acquired by Spotify in 2017 (following a series of lawsuits over unpaid royalties for many of the songs available for streaming), and the team officially turned over code (and responsibility) to the open source software community.

All of the issues defined in the process remain, and distributed ledger technologies remain at the center of ongoing efforts. The focus on use and reuse complements

interest in digital creation. The trend toward open cultural data is likely to continue; see, for example, Cultural Places, describing itself as “the first holistic platform in the cultural sector that connects visitors, institutions, artists, content creators and donors” (ibid.). But cross-platform solutions to the identification and sharing of data sets play a key role as decentralised technologies have the potential to build on the work of open cultural data pioneers (Sanderhoff 2014, Europeana 2018). Given the societal stakes of new data models and data-driven strategies for the creation of value, it is important to ensure that such developments are not simply considered issues of technology design (Rouvroy 2015, MSI-Net 2018). Initiatives such as “Artists Re:Thinking the Blockchain” highlight the urgency and richness of such multidisciplinary engagement, but also the complexities of reclaiming even parts of the terrain (and terminology) of technology development (Catlow et al 2017). But if the rollout of distributed ledger technologies is to amount to more than a new generation of digital rights managements tools, co-creative processes to foster the emergence of a truly open web will have to be organized.

4 Conclusion and Outlook: SPOT or Truth in the Era of Decentralised Technologies

The blockchain - both as the technology of distributed ledgers and the broader socio-technological dynamic emerging around this infrastructural core - is about the internet of value, facilitating transactions, applicable to a wide range of digital creative activities, promising significant support to digital entrepreneurial activities. Open “living lab” / prototyping methodologies to focus on the co-design of emerging technological systems.

Only a few years old, the idea of the blockchain as a stand-alone technology (rather than a data structure) is already undergoing conceptual and technological revision. Several communities are working on “blockless” distributed ledgers, so we may not even speak of “chains” in the near future. The issues remain, calling for artists and digital creators more generally to engage with the co-design of the decentralised technologies likely to shape their work in the future.

Current Focus in Co-Creation	Future Focus in Co-Creation
non-commercial > commercial	non-commercial <> commercial
linear business model development	non-linear business model development

stakeholder identity defines stakeholder contribution	stakeholder action facilitates flexible attribution of roles
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The search for the “single point of truth”, i.e. a comprehensive data model in digital creation is on. How do we - artists / digital creators - engage with this process? Can arts and culture create developments that are more than secondary to the dynamics of finance? Along with the Digital Single Market EU directive on the topic and the launch of a Blockchain Observatory and Forum, 22 European countries have already signed a Declaration on the establishment of a European Blockchain Partnership. This means that we also need to engage with this policy process that will soon frame co-creative activities in this area of tech design. Getting involved in a concrete design process offers us an opportunity to comprehend the stakes of this policy dynamic, generate a better understanding of how such technological developments frame our own activity, and explore how different trajectories of policy development affect our ability to engage in such activity. Spectrum can contribute a case study and co-creation approach to this process.

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